

Search Strategy Template

Example

TOPIC: The role of social media in elections

1 STEP 1: Identify the main concepts of your assignment topic

Concept 1	Concept 2	Concept 3
social media	elections	<i>not applicable in this example</i>

2 STEP 2: Think of as many keywords (including synonyms and alternative terms) as possible for each of those concepts

Concept 1	Concept 2	Concept 3
social media	elections	<i>not applicate in this example</i>
Twitter	Voting	
Facebook		
Instagram		

3 STEP 3: Combine keywords using Boolean Operators (AND, OR, NOT) and other search operators

Concept 1	(“social media” OR Twitter OR Facebook OR Instagram)
AND	AND
Concept 2	(elections OR voting)

NOTE:

- Place an **OR** in between alternatives for each concept and use brackets to group them together. You will not need brackets if there are multiple search boxes available on the database you are searching.
- Use inverted commas/quotation marks around terms, in this case “social media”
- Place an **AND** in between each concept to indicate that each must be included in any results.
- If you have more than two concepts add each set of alternatives, grouped by brackets with using AND in between each

Search Strategy Template

Blank

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Concept 1	Concept 2	Concept 3

2 **STEP 2:**
Think of as many keywords (including synonyms and alternative terms) as possible for each of those concepts

Concept 1	Concept 2	Concept 3

3 **STEP 3:**
Combine keywords using Boolean Operators (AND, OR, NOT) and other search operators

Concept 1	
AND	AND
Concept 2	
AND	AND
Concept 3	